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deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AADIL MOHAMMAD A** bearing USN **2SU20HO001** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ASTUDY ON CAPITAL STRUCTURE AND MARKET VALUE OF COMPANIES”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

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Dean
College of Management and Commerce

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Dean

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABOBACKER SIDDIQ** bearing USN **2SU20HO005** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ASTUDY ON CAPITAL STRUCTURE AND MARKET VALUE OF COMPANIES”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASIKA SASEENDRAN .K bearing USN **2SU20HO009** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**ASTUDY ON CAPITAL STRUCTURE AND MARKET VALUE OF COMPANIES**” in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AYSHA ZULFA** bearing USN **2SU20HO011** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ASTUDY ON CAPITAL STRUCTURE AND MARKET VALUE OF COMPANIES”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHAITALI P PUTHRAN** bearing USN **2SU20HO013** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE IMPACT OF ADVERTISING ON HOTEL AND TOURISM SERVICE DELIVERY (A CASE STUDY OF TOP 10 SELECTED HOTELS AT MANGALORE)”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms D R MANOJ bearing USN 2SU20HO014 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “THE IMPACT OF ADVERTISING ON HOTEL AND TOURISM SERVICE DELIVERY (A CASE STUDY OF TOP 10 SELECTED HOTELS AT MANGALORE)” in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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Dean
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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HANNATH SALEEMA** bearing USN **2SU20HO015** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE IMPACT OF ADVERTISING ON HOTEL AND TOURISM SERVICE DELIVERY (A CASE STUDY OF TOP 10 SELECTED HOTELS AT MANGALORE)”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **I B SINCHANA** bearing USN **2SU20HO016** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE IMPACT OF ADVERTISING ON HOTEL AND TOURISM SERVICE DELIVERY (A CASE STUDY OF TOP 10 SELECTED HOTELS AT MANGALORE)”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JISHNU.G** bearing USN **2SU20HO017** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE IMPACT OF ADVERTISING ON HOTEL AND TOURISM SERVICE DELIVERY (A CASE STUDY OF TOP 10 SELECTED HOTELS AT MANGALORE)”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KSHAMA D** bearing USN **2SU20HO019** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE IMPACT OF ADVERTISING ON HOTEL AND TOURISM SERVICE DELIVERY (A CASE STUDY OF TOP 10 SELECTED HOTELS AT MANGALORE)”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KUSHALAPPA K K** bearing USN **2SU20HO020** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE IMPACT OF ADVERTISING ON HOTEL AND TOURISM SERVICE DELIVERY (A CASE STUDY OF TOP 10 SELECTED HOTELS AT MANGALORE)”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **M.ABDUL SHAZIM** bearing USN **2SU20HO021** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE IMPACT OF ADVERTISING ON HOTEL AND TOURISM SERVICE DELIVERY (A CASE STUDY OF TOP 10 SELECTED HOTELS AT MANGALORE)”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHAMED ZAHEER** bearing USN **2SU20HO022** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“THE IMPACT OF ADVERTISING ON HOTEL AND TOURISM SERVICE DELIVERY (A CASE STUDY OF TOP 10 SELECTED HOTELS AT MANGALORE)”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHAMMAD RIZWAN** bearing USN **2SU20HO023** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“AUDIENCE RECEPTION OF MOBILE OUTDOOR ADVERTISING MESSAGES AS A STRATEGY FOR PRODUCT AWARENESS IN THE FOOD AND BEVERAGE INDUSTRY.”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD LAZIM ALI C.L** bearing USN **2SU20HO025** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“AUDIENCE RECEPTION OF MOBILE OUTDOOR ADVERTISING MESSAGES AS A STRATEGY FOR PRODUCT AWARENESS IN THE FOOD AND BEVERAGE INDUSTRY.”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED ANSAB M bearing USN 2SU20HO026 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “AUDIENCE RECEPTION OF MOBILE OUTDOOR ADVERTISING MESSAGES AS A STRATEGY FOR PRODUCT AWARENESS IN THE FOOD AND BEVERAGE INDUSTRY.” in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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Dean

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED YASIN M A bearing USN 2SU20HO028 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “AUDIENCE RECEPTION OF MOBILE OUTDOOR ADVERTISING MESSAGES AS A STRATEGY FOR PRODUCT AWARENESS IN THE FOOD AND BEVERAGE INDUSTRY.” in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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Dean

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED RIZWAN L E** bearing USN **2SU20HO033** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“AUDIENCE RECEPTION OF MOBILE OUTDOOR ADVERTISING MESSAGES AS A STRATEGY FOR PRODUCT AWARENESS IN THE FOOD AND BEVERAGE INDUSTRY.”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED THAHIR** bearing USN **2SU20HO034** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ROLE OF MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM IN ENHANCING SALES”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIDEESH KUMAR** bearing USN **2SU20HO035** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ROLE OF MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM IN ENHANCING SALES”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIKHIL N SHETTY** bearing USN **2SU20HO036** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ROLE OF MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM IN ENHANCING SALES”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **O K FAWAZ** bearing USN **2SU20HO037** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ROLE OF MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM IN ENHANCING SALES”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRATHEEK SURATHKAL bearing USN 2SU20HO038 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “ROLE OF MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM IN ENHANCING SALES” in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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Dean

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deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAKESH RAJ URS L** bearing USN **2SU20HO041** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ROLE OF MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM IN ENHANCING SALES”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAKSHITHA** bearing USN **2SU20HO042** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ROLE OF MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM IN ENHANCING SALES”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDRA PRIMAL MARTIS** bearing USN **2SU20HO044** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“ROLE OF MARKETING INFORMATION SYSTEM IN ENHANCING SALES”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAHABAS T bearing USN **2SU20HO045** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“MARKET INTEREST RATES AND COMMERCIAL BANK PROFITABILITY: (A CASE STUDY OF SBI BANK IN DK DISTRICTS.)”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL RAZIK** bearing USN **2SU20CM002** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“COST ACCOUNTING INFORMATION AND PRODUCT COSTING IN SELECTED PAINT MANUFACTURING COMPANIES”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHAY ULLAS PAI** bearing USN **2SU20CM003** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**COST ACCOUNTING INFORMATION AND PRODUCT COSTING IN SELECTED PAINT MANUFACTURING COMPANIES**” in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SALMAN FARISH** bearing USN **2SU20CM029** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“AN EVALUATION OF MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING TECHNIQUES ON ORGANIZATION DECISION MAKING PROCESS”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SARATH PONNARASSERY SAJY** bearing USN **2SU20CM030** has completed his/her minor project on the topic “**AN EVALUATION OF MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING TECHNIQUES ON ORGANIZATION DECISION MAKING PROCESS**” in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREYA** bearing USN **2SU20CM032** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“AN EVALUATION OF MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING TECHNIQUES ON ORGANIZATION DECISION MAKING PROCESS”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREERAG RAVINDRAN bearing USN 2SU20CM033 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “AN EVALUATION OF MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING TECHNIQUES ON ORGANIZATION DECISION MAKING PROCESS” in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASEEL SALIQ SHEIKH bearing USN 2SU20AC002 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “COST-VOLUME-PROFIT ANALYSIS AS A MANAGEMENT TOOL FOR DECISION MAKING A CASE STUDY OF INDIAN BREWERIES LTD” in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, consisting of stylized, cursive letters, is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED RUKAIL.M bearing USN 2SU20AC003 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “COST-VOLUME-PROFIT ANALYSIS AS A MANAGEMENT TOOL FOR DECISION MAKING A CASE STUDY OF INDIAN BREWERIES LTD” in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED DILSHAD.K.S** bearing USN **2SU20AC004** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“COST-VOLUME-PROFIT ANALYSIS AS A MANAGEMENT TOOL FOR DECISION MAKING A CASE STUDY OF INDIAN BREWERIES LTD”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMAD HAFIS K M P** bearing USN **2SU20AC005** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“COST-VOLUME-PROFIT ANALYSIS AS A MANAGEMENT TOOL FOR DECISION MAKING A CASE STUDY OF INDIAN BREWERIES LTD”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NITHIN** bearing USN **2SU20AC006** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“COST-VOLUME-PROFIT ANALYSIS AS A MANAGEMENT TOOL FOR DECISION MAKING A CASE STUDY OF INDIAN BREWERIES LTD”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAVIKIRAN BASAVARAJ CHINNAPUR** bearing USN **2SU20AC007** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“COST-VOLUME-PROFIT ANALYSIS AS A MANAGEMENT TOOL FOR DECISION MAKING A CASE STUDY OF INDIAN BREWERIES LTD”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj'.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
College of Management and Commerce
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANKALP BOGAR bearing USN 2SU20AC008 has completed his/her minor project on the topic “COST-VOLUME-PROFIT ANALYSIS AS A MANAGEMENT TOOL FOR DECISION MAKING A CASE STUDY OF INDIAN BREWERIES LTD” in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

Prof. Keerthan Raj
Dean
College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SWATI PREMAN** bearing USN **2SU20AC009** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“COST-VOLUME-PROFIT ANALYSIS AS A MANAGEMENT TOOL FOR DECISION MAKING A CASE STUDY OF INDIAN BREWERIES LTD”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, consisting of stylized, cursive letters, is positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

College of Management and Commerce

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore

College of Management and Commerce

www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

deancmc@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THASLIMA** bearing USN **2SU20AC010** has completed his/her minor project on the topic **“COST-VOLUME-PROFIT ANALYSIS AS A MANAGEMENT TOOL FOR DECISION MAKING A CASE STUDY OF INDIAN BREWERIES LTD”** in the Second year of the B.Com programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, consisting of a series of loops and a long horizontal stroke, positioned above the name of the Dean.

Prof. Keerthan Raj

Dean

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